

Chemistry in 2000 A.D. †

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Chemistry is the science of all sciences and art of all arts. The search for 'elixir of life' and the 'philosopher's stone' to provide mankind with freedom from disease and freedom from want continues. A substantial headway has already been made. In fact, acceleration in the rate of progress in chemical research in the last decade and the spate of startling discoveries made would justify an in-pur of science-fiction on any prognostication about the chemical pathways to be followed at the turn of this century. In view of vast canvas of the subject of chemistry, with its inroads into molecular biology, nuclear physics and technology in general, covering the properties of all matter, living and non-living and further knowing that so many separate branches of science are so intimately interwoven, making isolated predictions would hardly have much sense. Prudence demands confining oneself to a rather narrow range of problems and extrapolate a given function for reliable prediction over a rather small period of time of ten or twenty years. The extrapolation has to be in consonance strictly with the laws of quantum mechanics and statistical physics, governing the structure of matter. In the context of human welfare, the encouraging results of experiments on DNA synthesis, new pathways in medicinal chemistry, new materials like composites and the astonishing superconducting materials and finally the recent success in the nuclear-fusion experiments for power generation get precedence in this discussion.

Undoubtedly, one of the most cherished and exciting realm of chemical research in the last few decades has been the exploration of chemical synthesis of DNA and DNA analogues which typify living matter. It has been established that the DNA molecule, consisting of a long back-bone chain and side-chains of four types of nucleotide bases, namely thymine, cytosine, adenine and guanine, in a double helical structure, serves as a matrix for reproducing another identical DNA molecule in the process of cell division and it also produces the matrix of RNA molecules which, in turn, produce the units of which the various proteins are composed. The messenger RNA (mRNA), an exact copy of a section of DNA molecule of length of one cistron which is approximately a sequence of a thousand nucleotides, responsible for the production of a polypeptide containing a chain of amino-acids joined by peptide linkage, set out to synthesise protein molecules in ribosomes, the amino-acid being provided by the transfer RNA (tRNA) molecules. This is the way

an organism functions. The responsibility of genes for hereditary characters is unambiguously associated with its chemical function in the synthesis of protein molecules. Sequencing of amino-acids in the proteins is of prime importance. "Surprisingly, there is only a slight difference in the sequence of amino-acids in the haemoglobin molecules of man, the horse, the bull and the mosquito". Success in research work on the structure of protein molecules, mechanism of transmission of hereditary characters, atomic interpretation of mutation and intervention in biochemical synthesis appears to have paved the way for "cultivation of living organism in chemical flask and the improvement of organism by correcting flaws due to non-selective gene control of heredity characteristic". The dream may become a reality at the turn of the century but obstacles on the way must be first removed.

The phosphoramidite method of DNA synthesis developed by Caruthers¹ can be used for rapid (one day or less) preparation of deoxyoligonucleotides of the size of *lac* operator. It has been shown to be adaptable to automated DNA synthesis machines. Very high yields of relatively pure polynucleotides having hundred or more mononucleotides can be obtained. This method used silica as an inert matrix in place of organic matrices for attachment of growing DNA strand. The problem of side-products and intermediates dominating the final reaction mixture, is further avoided due to discovery of a new class of stable trivalent phosphorus synthons, the deoxynucleoside 3'-phosphoramidites. This method can also be extended to include the synthesis of oligoribonucleotides, 2'-*O*-methyloligoribonucleotides, oligoaribonucleotides and α -DNA. But the challenge remains for developing methods for large-scale synthesis of oligonucleotides and oligonucleotide analogues. "Efforts will have to be made in the coming years to develop synthesis protocols for analogues linked through sulphur, nitrogen, carbon to phosphorus".

As far as DNA sequencing² is concerned, big jumps in DNA sequencing rates came from the introduction of 'plus and minus' method in 1975 which was used to sequence a bacteriophage. This gave way to chain-termination method called the dideoxy method or Sanger method which was applied to larger genomes of human mitochondrial DNA. The longest human sequence determined (human growth hormone gene region) is 66 kb (EMBL

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database) and 73 kb (human β -globin gene region : GenBank). In 100 kb or more range, only the genomes of herpesviruses and chloroplasts have been determined. The new technologies of fluorescent sequencing based on dideoxy method in the form of the Applied Biosystems machine (ABI) now capable of determining 24 sequences in a day and giving highly accurate readings up to 500 or so, and the Multiplexing sequencing based on cloning of DNA into approximately 40 different vectors, each distinguished by a unique sequence that can be probed on a blot of sequencing gel, may go a long way to solve the problem of the speed of sequencing to cope with deducing the functions of the gene sequences produced by DNA sequencing. "In coming years, there is prospect of a machine that will automate both sequencing and separation, together in a box. However, sequencing large areas of human genome with present-day technology does not seem to be practical and if attempted, it may entail a vast amount of expenditure and also may be very time-consuming. "Reaction on solid support and increasing automation with miniaturisation perhaps would simplify matters".

Perhaps the most profound impact of our ability to manipulate DNA will come in the realm of medicinal chemistry. Knowledge on genetically engineered drug discovery tools has been increasing. Polymerase chain reaction (PCR) technique is an enzymatic method for the *in-vitro* amplification of specific DNA fragments. This knowledge has revolutionised the search for sub-species. Recombinantly produced reagents of potential application to drug discovery have been classified into three categories³: isolated or cell-surface expressed enzymes (with catalytic functions), receptors (with signal transduction function) and binding proteins (with cellular adhesion properties). In the coming years, "regulation of inducible or tissue specific gene expression may become an important method for pharmacological intervention".

One of the most recent pathway which has a tremendous potential is the possibility of use of antisense nucleic acids⁴ as pharmaceutical agents. "The strand of RNA which is translated into a protein is termed the sense or the plus strand; the strand complementary to the sense strand is the antisense or minus strand. The introduction of a specific antisense RNA into a cell can markedly inhibit the functioning of the sense strand". The mechanism is not yet fully understood. It has been proposed that "intracellular formation of highly specific sense-antisense hybrids" may impair the functioning of mRNA. It is possible to introduce antisense DNA or RNA directly into cells or else DNA molecules capable of producing antisense RNA may be transfected into the cell. The drugs produced by exploiting this technology may be useful as anti-cancer, anti-viral agents. But before full use can be made of the pharmaceutical properties of these compounds, the problem of their degradation by the nucleases present in abundance in the

plasma and also within the cell must be solved. Also large quantities of these will have to be produced as large concentration would be required. The main point also remains a challenge for the future workers in so far as the effectiveness of antisense drugs has not been determined for the *in vivo* systems.

Another epoch making discovery made recently relates to the discovery of a new class of enzymes which may be called the designer enzymes. These are really catalytic antibodies⁵. "Antibodies are proteins generated by the immune system to recognise foreign entities and initiate their neutralisation or destruction. They are capable of recognising with high affinity a diverse spectrum of molecules ranging in size from 6 to 35 Å. A typical IgG antibody has a molecular weight of 150 000 kD with two ligand-combining regions. The combining sites are defined by the hypervariable regions of light and heavy polypeptide chains (V_L and V_H respectively) and located in to the first 110 amino-terminal residues of these polypeptides. More than 10⁸ different antibody molecules are available through recombination of V_L and V_H genes, making the antibody pool a particularly rich source of molecular specificities". Starting from Kohler and Milstein's preparation of immortalised immune cell hybrids that produced mitochondrial bodies, a large number of chemical transformations have been achieved; amide hydrolysis, carbonate-, esters-lactonisation, aminolysis, lipase activity, concerted rearrangements, β -eliminations and redox reactions can be cited as examples. This, therefore may provide an unlimited ability to select a specific catalyst for the desired chemical transformation of any particular reactant; really the chemist's dream come true! Also it has been demonstrated that the antibodies can be generated to recognise specific tumour antigens and then carry out catalytic reaction to mediate the destruction of these tumour cells. Evidently these applications arise out of inherent properties of antibodies and specially tailored catalytic properties. But one has to remember that the antibodies have rigid structures capable of binding with high affinity to antigens. They do not have the flexibility of enzymes which permit the access of substrates to the active site and efficient dissociation of products. The future research would therefore be directed to "narrow the gap between antibodies and enzymes".

It has been shown only very recently that electrophilic and photoactivated agents may be useful as receptor selective irreversible probes⁶. These ligands attach themselves irreversibly in a covalent bond at or near the specific binding-site. Of course, these have the capacity to recognise the specific binding-site easily. The coming years would perhaps see preparation of more selective, high affinity irreversible ligands which will aid in receptor characterisation and finally in drug design.

The latest trend in the methods of medicinal chemistry, relates to molecular modelling⁷. "In

computer-assisted drug-design, molecular modelling systems provide purposeful tools for building, visualising, analysing, storing models of complex molecular systems that can help interpret structure-activity relationship". 'Direct' and 'indirect' design are the two major strategies used in the conception of new drugs. "In the first approach, the three-dimensional features of a known receptor-site are directly covered and in the latter, the design is based on the comparative analysis of the structural features of known active and inactive molecules that are interpreted in terms of complementarity with a hypothetical receptor-site model". Computer programmes like ORTEP, FRODO, AMBER CAMSEQ, PCILO and CHARMM have been combined to give high performance computing graphics for molecular modelling. In fact, much higher levels of computer automation, rationalisation and quantification are needed to make quantitative predictions of activity. Also, the current methods in molecular modelling/computer-assisted drug-design still indispensably need the creativity of the medicinal chemist's mind.

Instrumentationwise, a very powerful tool for quantitative determination of biodistribution of drugs in man and their short-term pharmacokinetics is now available in the form of positron emission tomography (PET)⁸. It is a tracer method capable of measuring the temporal and spatial concentration of radioactivity in a volume element of a living tissue. "The method is safe and precise and comparatively very quick. What is very attractive about this method is the fact that there is a lot of flexibility about the use of physiological isotopes for labelling. C^{11} ($t_{1/2}=204$ min), F^{18} ($t_{1/2}=110$ min), O^{15} ($t_{1/2}=2$ min), N^{13} ($t_{1/2}=10$ min) may be used in this radiotracer method".

Chemistry has provided mankind with materials of desired properties for use in diverse fields in the form of metallic alloys, ceramics and polymers. We know that metallic crystals consist of three-dimensional space-lattices immersed in an electron gas. Ionic crystals which comprise a large number of inorganic compounds like silicates, have spherical close-packed positive and negative ions. In molecules, groups of atoms have shared electrons. Joining of atoms in long chains/threads gives rise to macromolecules. Strength of a material is a function of bonds between ions or atoms and follows the laws of physical chemistry. Therefore, to increase the strength of the material, it would be necessary to decrease the number of internal defects in crystal lattices. The other course open is to combine materials. In nature, wood consists of strong and flexible cellulose fibres surrounded by and held together by a stiffer material, lignin. The chemist can combine niobium with niobium carbide to get strong material in which good electrical properties are retained. Very fine threads of boron immersed in fused aluminium gives a very strong and light new material. Exploiting this idea, now it is well established that the combined materials which are defined as Composites may well meet the requirements for material needed for aerospace,

underwater, and transportation applications which are not answered by conventional materials like metallic alloys, ceramics and polymers. Generally, composite materials are composed of two phases—the matrix and the dispersed phase, the properties of the composites being a function of the constituent phases, their relative amounts and shape, size, orientation of the particles of the dispersed phase⁹. These can be dispersion strengthened (like thoria dispersed in nickel) where particle diameter can be between 0.1 and 0.1 μm dispersed in a volume concentration up to 15%; particle reinforced (like a cermet, e.g. a refractory carbide like tungsten carbide or titanium carbide in a matrix of a metal like cobalt or nickel) where particle size can be >1 μm and concentration 20–40 volume %; and fibre reinforced (like carbon black added to rubber to enhance tensile strength or rubber added to thermoplastics like polystyrene to remove brittleness) where the fibre diameter can vary from a micrometer to several mills and volume concentration $\sim 70\%$. The mechanical properties of continuous and aligned fibre composites are highly anisotropic. Fibreglass-reinforced composites have a special focus. However these are not stiff enough and rigid enough to be used in airplane structures and bridge structures. Plastics impregnated with graphite fibres are finding more use in aircraft industry due to better resistance to transportation and corrosion chemicals. In the coming years, the use SiC , Si_3N_4 in plastic matrix may be tried. Borosic-aluminium composites externally coated with SiC hold good promise for use at high temperatures. A relatively new fibre-reinforced composite is the hybrid obtained by using two or more different kinds of fibres in a single matrix, for example, graphite and glass fibres incorporated into a polymer resin. These are used for lightweight land, water and air transport structural components because their failure under tension is non-catastrophic. Advanced composites are rapidly emerging as the primary material for use in near-term and next-generation aircraft. Creating¹⁰ composites in which "hardness of diamond, the elasticity of rubber, the transparency of cut-glass, the conductivity of copper, the magnetic properties of iron and the light weight of aluminium are united", will be the goal of research in the next century!

The discovery of high temperature superconducting material in 1986 has generated great excitement and the whole scenario of superconductivity has undergone a dramatic change. Muller and Bendorz¹¹ discovered in 1986 that a ceramic material, the mixed metal oxide, La-Ba-Cu-O became superconducting at about 30 K. In 1987, Chu and his collaborators¹² made an exciting announcement, $\text{YBa}_2\text{Cu}_3\text{U}_{7-8}$ exhibited superconducting property at about 90 K. This was the first superconductor at liquid nitrogen temperature of 77 K and gave a workable range for superconductors as liquid nitrogen is much cheaper as compared to liquid helium which was required to use some metals and alloys for superconducting properties when the

discovery of this property was made in 1911 by H. K. Onnes. These observations on ceramic materials giving superconducting property were startling as no one would have ordinarily thought of such property in ceramics; the first experiments in this connection though were made by Johnson *et al.*¹³ in 1973 and Sleight *et al.*¹⁴ in 1975 who had respectively described LiTi_2O_4 and $\text{BaPb}_{1-x}\text{Bi}_x\text{O}_{3-\delta}$ both having a critical temperature (T_c) about 13 K. The more recently discovered¹⁵ $\text{Bi}_2\text{Sr}_2\text{Ca}_n\text{Cu}_{n+1}\text{O}_{2n+6}$ has a T_c of 90 K and $\text{Tl}_2\text{Sr}_2\text{Ca}_n\text{Cu}_{n+1}\text{O}_{2n+6}$ gives a T_c of about 125 K. The varying stoichiometry can be utilised to tailor the desired property in the material. Change in oxygen stoichiometry (value of δ) is known to make $\text{YBa}_2\text{Cu}_3\text{O}_{7-\delta}$ a superconductor ($T_c = -60$ K) at value 0.2 to 0.55. A higher value makes it a non-conductor but a lower value of 0 to 0.2 raises the T_c to 90 K. In the two superconducting states, the crystal axes change from $a=b < c/3$ to $a < b < c/3$ to $a < b = c/3$. The structure of Y-Ba-Cu-O in the fully loaded ($\delta=0$) state has been shown¹⁶ to have "two planes of copper oxide straddling a sheet of yttrium atoms and copper oxide chains sandwiched between two barium oxide planes which unload oxygen. Only half the oxygen sites are occupied forming -O-Cu-O-Cu- chains and the structure is orthorhombic" as the chains are formed only in b direction, making this axis longer. A rise in temperature causes disorder with oxygen changing sites and also diffusing on surface, the resulting unloading making it a tetragonal system with equal a and b axes. The superconducting property is given only by the orthorhombic material. High temperature superconductivity (HTSC) offers advantage in electricity generation, nuclear-fusion by way of giving magnets of ultra-high field strength and in energy storage where 100% efficiency, never before attained can be achieved. In transportation, the best use can be made utilising the high strength magnetic field, for magnetically-levitated rail transportation and magnetic ship propulsion. It is possible to develop superconducting quantum interface device (SQUID) which can detect extremely weak magnetic fields as those in the human brain and heart. The exotic uses of the superconducting materials are bound to change the very lifestyle of man in the coming times. The phenomenon has, however, eluded a precise theoretical interpretation and it is difficult to say whether the HTSC would ever be observed at room temperature. There is an intense research activity being pursued with frantic zeal to pin down the phenomenon and if room temperature HTSC can be achieved, the face of the world would change beyond comprehension!

Of primary importance in laying the material foundation of society and bettering the life of man, are the available power resources of the world. In our times, the extremely high rate of industrial development and agricultural mechanisation as well as the rapid increase in the world population have caused an ever greater consumption of fuel so much so that by all reckonings, the world fuel resources

would be exhausted in the next twenty or fifty years. A fuller use of nuclear energy with adequate precaution for disposal of radioactive waste may, therefore, be a way for solving the problem. U-235, the fissionable isotope, suitable for production of power from nuclear energy, occurs in the nature only 0.7 percent of natural uranium which is itself in scant deposits in the earth. However, the economy is well worked out by using the 'breeder reactors' involving uranium-plutonium conversion. The problem of residual radioactive products puts a limit to the number of such reactors being commissioned for service.

The efforts, therefore, were directed towards tapping power from controlled thermonuclear reactions. Extremely high temperature of the order of hundred million degrees is essential for sustaining the reaction. The simplest reaction perhaps is the bimolecular reaction of nuclei of gaseous deuterium:

Even if a sufficiently high temperature is attained by passing a strong current through the active material, there is the problem of the shell material being vapourised at that temperature. Magnetic confinement of the reaction has been used to reduce heat transfer to the reaction shell. An easier reaction may be

considering the cross-section and reaction rate constants. But in this case tritium must be first synthesised. The initial charge of T_1^3 can be obtained in the usual atomic reactors and then 'bred'. This may be done by surrounding the reactor with another shell made of lithium compounds and the neutron slowed down in the Li-shell would give the reaction:

In fact, the D-D reaction proceeds in two steps: $\text{D}_1^2 + \text{D}_1^2 = \text{T}_1^3 + \text{p}_1^1$ and $\text{T}_1^3 + \text{D}_1^2 = \text{He}_2^4 + \text{n}_0^1$. Only last month the team working on the Joint European Torus (JET) experimental fusion reactor in Oxfordshire succeeded in producing nearly two megawatts of power as announced by the JET spokesman, John Maple¹⁷. In this experiment the scientists used a tiny amount of tritium (about 0.2 g) and this is the first time that a significant amount of power has been obtained from controlled nuclear-fusion reaction. The peak fusion power generated reached about 2 MW in a pulse lasting for two seconds. According to JET scientists, the performance has to be improved by a factor of five for commercial uses and it may take 25 to 50 years according to Paul-Henri Rebut, the Director of JET. The JET has the cooperation of scientists from thirteen countries from Europe. Evidently, the energy-creating capability of the sun has been simulated and commercial production of power using this technique, when achieved, would assure mankind about his sustenance in the face of threat of exhaustion of conventional fuel resources. The waste residues of this reaction is much less radioactive than the ones given

by fission power stations and the greatest advantage over the fossil fuels is that it does not pollute.

A few facets of chemical research in the coming years have been mentioned here. In fact, it is beyond imagination to specify the way these sensational discoveries, that may be on the cards, would transform our life !

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